

Resources	Comment	URL
Online resources (viewing mostly)		
GeoSvalbard	Geological maps (vector and images), selected cross-sections, sample and DOM locations	https://geokart.npolar.no/geologi/GeoSvalbard/
Svalbardkartet	Multi-disciplinary online portal including geology, an outdated claim map, national parks etc.	https://geokart.npolar.no/Html5Viewer/index.html?viewer=Svalbardkartet
TopoSvalbard	Topographic map including aerial imagery, old	https://toposvalbard.npolar.no/
VRSvalbard	Photosphere-based atlas of Svalbard's geology	http://www.vrsvalbard.com
Svalbox	Digital outcrop models in the context of regional geology	http://portal.svalbox.no
Online resources (for direct streaming to GIS software and data download)		
Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI) geodata	Basemap services from NPI, including topography, satellite imagery and most layers as available on Svalbardkartet	https://geodata.npolar.no/
Svalbox	Digital outcrop models in the context of regional geology	http://portal.svalbox.no
Data portals		
BGR Arctic Repository	Data repository of Germany's Geological Survey (BGR) with an Arctic focus, including outcrop data and geophysical profiles	https://arctic.bgr.de/mapapps4/resources/apps/arktis/index.html?lang=en
AWI seismic profile map	The map will be linked very soon with the Pangaea database to directly access available profiles there. The navigation is not yet available that way.	https://maps.awi.de/awimaps/projects/public/?cu=geophysics_arctic#home
AWI sediment echosounder data	e.g., from cruises on RV Polarstern, RV Maria S. Merian, RV Heincke	Archived on PANGAEA. https://www.pangaea.de/?q=sediment+echo+sounding&maxlat=81.27311926447925&minlon=2.348750948196061&maxlon=33.63781344819606&minlat=76.88785354508799
NGU geodata portal	Data portal of the Norwegian Geological Survey	https://geo.ngu.no/geoscienceportalopen/Results?bookmark=0bf79eb071474cd7a92240d4360b84db
Norwegian Offshore Directorate data portal	Area is not open for petroleum exploration around Svalbard and seismic data are not available for open download	https://www.sodir.no/en/diskos/public-portal/